

PEDAGOGY

SETTING THE PROBLEM IN TEXTBOOKS AND METHODOLOGICAL MATERIALS FOR TEACHERS

Abbasova S.

Candidate of pedagogical sciences, docent

Abstract

The situation of teaching includes the existence of a problem (contradiction) and the way to solve it. That is, the teacher should put a problem in front of the children, deeply understand the nature of the question, and also imagine how the children can answer. He should always be ready to help students not get confused in the formulation of problems and discussions. Creating a learning situation is a process of conducting problem-based learning.

Keywords: Active training, cognitive activity, methodological tools, types of work, reproductive.

The teaching situation ensures creative assimilation of knowledge by students through dialogue with the teacher. This method allows to develop cognition and communication skills, provides effective development of high-quality knowledge, intelligence and creative abilities, education of an active personality.

By creating a learning situation, the teaching method is aimed at:

- 1) identification of the problem (difficulties);
- 2) choosing a solution to the problem;
- 3) ability to work with information;
- 4) listening and understanding other people;
- 5) ability to work in a group.

Teacher's duty:

- creating learning situations (determining the pedagogical task (developing writing skills);
- choose the teaching material;
- to determine the way of organizing the learning situation (how to start, what to do for everyone);
- predict possible actions of children;
- turning training tasks into learning situations (not only with the learning task, but also its "regulation" - putting this task in conditions that encourage children to be active, create motivation for learning).

Types of learning situations:

1. Selection. A number of ready-made solutions are provided, including incorrect ones. You need to choose the right one.
2. Uncertainty. Uncertain decisions due to lack of information.
3. Surprise. It causes surprising unusualness, paradoxically.
4. Conflict. A situation that thinks otherwise.
5. Incompatibility. It does not "fit" existing practices and ideas. [3, p.13-14]

The requirements for carrying out the study are:

- that students have basic knowledge and skills in subjects (have program material);
- ability to work independently;
- the value of the expected training results;
- the ability to change the way of thinking.

In the lesson of learning new material, two connections should be worked out: the formulation of an educational problem and the search for its solution. The formation of the educational problem and the search for a solution are carried out by students during a specially structured dialogue.

Dialogue is at the heart of any learning situation, and dialogue is essential to resolving this situation.

Methods of creating a learning situation with problem formulation and solving occur in three stages of lessons:

- 1) updating knowledge.
- 2) statement of the problem.
- 3) "discovery" of new knowledge by children.

"Discovery" of new knowledge by children is based on some mental operations, so tasks that teach this mental operation should be included in the stage of updating knowledge. Thought must be put into "form". Therefore, in the actualization of knowledge, it is necessary to include tasks of this type: find the excess, divide into groups, compare and show the difference, tasks for the development of variant thinking, attention, memory, etc. In the final task, "complexity" is planned. Completion of the stage of updating knowledge is associated with the identification of "difficulties" in the activity. [2, p.101]

To create a learning situation means to present students with a sense of surprise or any contradiction that arises in relation to difficulties. For example: it is enough to look at the methods of creating educational situations in the lessons of the special course "Prevention of spelling errors".

Methodical material for Azerbaijani language lessons is prepared according to demand. At the heart of the outline plans is a modern approach to learning.

Various innovative techniques, methods and forms were used during the development of lessons. The realities of modern life require students to develop a creative approach to learning, so it is rational to apply group work to lessons in order to understand the importance of teamwork, develop research skills, deepen, systematize and summarize the material.

Lessons in groups assume the presence of children with a high, sufficient, medium and low level of knowledge in each group. Groups can be permanent or changing (depending on their deep goals and tasks, the degree of complexity, the level of mastery of the material, the wishes of the students). Improving speech culture is one of the main goals of learning at this stage, so it is appropriate to include elements of literature in Azerbaijani language classes. It also helps students to have a coherent understanding of the texts.

In the methodical materials presented for class V, a sufficient amount of different materials have been selected for all these types of work, so that each teacher can choose the necessary option, focusing on his class. [7, p.13] The presented textbook set consists of two books: a textbook and a teacher. funds for (MMV). According to this set, it is planned to teach the Azerbaijani language in 6 sections. In the 5th grade, the subject of the Azerbaijani language is taught for 5 hours a week for 34 weeks (170 hours).

A small summative assessment (KSQ) is carried out no earlier than 4 weeks and no later than 6 weeks, and each educational stage covering this period corresponds to a certain section (topic) reflected in the textbook. A major summative assessment (BSQ) is conducted at the end of each semester. The number of hours allocated for each section includes 1 hour for KSQ. Hours intended for BSQ are not reflected in the schedule. The reading and listening materials, as well as the speaking and writing activities presented in each unit, are related to the topic of that unit.

Materials related to language rules are divided into sections as follows: Section I – the sound and letter composition of the word (phonetics); Section II – semantic features of the word (lexicon); Section III – word composition and formation methods (word creation); Section IV – words denoting name, sign, action (morphology); Section V – spelling of compound words. Section VI - types of sentences according to purpose and intonation, punctuation in dialogue. At the end of each section, the textbook provides materials for repeated lessons on the language rules taught in the corresponding section. [8, p. 4]

Tasks of various levels of complexity combine knowledge of theoretical material in practice, allowing not only to perform training exercises of a reproductive nature, but also to use the creative component that contributes to the further development of the individual, the manifestation of activity, and also increases interest in the subject.

The manual will help novice teachers to acquire the first methodical skills, and will give experienced teachers the opportunity to diversify the methodical techniques used in the lesson. Plans are designed taking into account the age characteristics of students and contain not only educational material, but also game tasks that develop the creative activity of schoolchildren, take them to the interesting country of the Azerbaijani language and help them to remember easily. The proposed coursework will provide practical help in choosing the types of training and control work that are fully presented and meet the requirements of the National Curriculum for the Azerbaijani language for grades V-XI.

Methodical resources are designed for creative use by diversifying the methods of presenting the material. Training can be effective if there is a qualitative change in training methods, and attention is paid to the active inclusion of thinking in the process of cognition and knowledge acquisition. The concept of "active learning method" characterizes learning based on active cognitive activity in the process of cooperation with other

participants of the educational process. Often, the concept of "interactive teaching methods" is used as a synonym of this concept.

Active learning is a set of ways of organizing and managing teaching and cognitive activity, which are characterized by the following: creation of a cognitive problem situation by the teacher; stimulating the active research position of students in the process of solving the problem situation; creating conditions for independent discovery, assimilation and assimilation of new knowledge for students. The essence of this approach to teaching is that training is not based on enriching students' memory with new knowledge, but on the systematic development of thinking and skills for self-assimilation and assimilation of knowledge. [2, p. 114]

The main condition for learning in this case is the need for the child to consciously isolate the educational task as a cognitive task: what to learn, why to learn, how to learn and what results it will lead to. The teacher's position is that of a "facilitator". The main function that determines the role of the teacher in active learning as a guide on the way to knowledge is called facilitation (creating favorable conditions). It is a new type of teacher leadership, based on the joint activity of students and teachers, aimed at achieving a common educational goal. At the same time, the teacher does not rule the classroom as an undisputed authority and does not stand outside of it.

He cooperates with him in a systematic and purposeful way: he organizes problematic situations, helps students formulate research problems, provides methodical assistance in solving them, directs and shows the way to acquire knowledge. The task of the teacher-facilitator is to teach learning, that is, to help the child: master the main components of the learning activity; to master in practice the set of mental methods and methods necessary for the acquisition and application of knowledge. This curriculum has an action quality and is designed to help each student become a competent, independent researcher, independently acquire the necessary knowledge, and become a lifelong learner.

However, in order to implement such a training scheme, the teacher should not only understand the role of a guide in the path of acquiring knowledge, but also know its specific functions and be able to apply them in practice. For this, first of all, it is necessary to understand the facilitation process itself: facilitation as a process is the process of organizing the discussion, activating the students by effectively using guiding, guiding questions, leading to the discovery of new knowledge; the main feature of facilitation is that new knowledge is acquired not by the teacher, but by the students; the position of the facilitator, whose main function is to encourage thinking and guide it in the right direction. The main goal of the facilitation approach is to fully satisfy cognitive and creative needs and create opportunities for students' self-realization.

Since active learning methods are based on conducting research for the purpose of discovering new knowledge, active teaching itself is based on the laws of conducting research.

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